

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report will describe the improvements to SR-ESMs in Cycles 1 and 2 (including output, and workflows) and will assess readiness for the final preparations for the production simulations.

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1 Executive summary

The purpose of this report is to summarise the readiness of the SR-ESMs for performing the Cycle 3 nextGEMS simulations, in advance of final preparation for the production simulations. We summarise both the changes made so far for improving ICON and IFS-FESOM/NEMO, and the remaining challenges that are currently being tackled. We also highlight the experiences in organizing and implementing community input through Hackathons, and how this contributed to develop the SR-ESMs and to ensure their usability for the applications.

The report shows that the two storm-resolving Earth System Models (SR-ESM), ICON and IFS-FESOM/NEMO, will be ready for the next cycle of nextGEMS, Cycle 3, within the next few weeks. This concerns both technical readiness as well as climate-readiness. Both SR-ESMs are also in a good position for the production runs that will be started by the end of 2023.

2 Conclusion & Results

With respect to model climate-readiness, the ICON and IFS-FESOM/NEMO configurations have seen great progress with respect to fixing energy and water imbalances, as summarised below.

For ICON, a major hurdle for long climate integrations has been the large net energy flux imbalance at the top of the atmosphere (-5 W m^{-2}). This imbalance was caused by an energy leak in the atmosphere component of the model; in particular, the leaks were identified in the microphysics, and in the turbulence and dynamics schemes of the model. To address these issues, the micro-physics and turbulence schemes were rewritten. Other updates were added for the land (new land maps based on high resolution observations) and the ocean (new vertical coordinate in the ocean to allow for thin layers at the model top). The hydrological discharge from land to ocean now also works with thin ocean layers in high resolution configurations.

In preparation for multi-year coupled simulations with the IFS, the atmospheric water and energy imbalances as well as the top-of-atmosphere imbalances of longwave and shortwave radiation have been strongly reduced, keeping all imbalances below 1 W m^{-2} . This will reduce the drift in global-mean 2m temperature to a minimum in the Cycle 3 simulations. In addition, the representation of several processes that are important for the climate system (atmosphere, land and ocean) have become more realistic. The key model updates include: (i) reduced cloud base mass flux in the convection scheme, (ii) introduction of a new multi-layer snow scheme, and (iii) new high-resolution ocean grid, NG5, which is used in FESOM.

With respect to technical readiness, ICON has demonstrated that the necessary functionality for multi-year integrations is there. Further progress has been made with the atmospheric component of ICON in making effective use of GPUs on several compute systems. The ocean component is still relying on CPUs, but the model can be used in a hybrid configuration as well, where the atmosphere runs on a GPU cluster and the ocean on the CPU cluster of the same compute centre.

For the IFS, technical developments were centered around using the "Real Applications on Parallel Systems" portable environment (short RAPS) in different supercomputer environments; and around extending IFS capabilities for performing multi-year simulations. Another stream of development dealt with optimising data workflows and model performance by writing simulation output with the forecast database software (FDB), as well as with multIO postprocessing

pipelines.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP2	Relevance in this deliverable?
Organizing simulation output from the pre-existing ICON and IFS DYAMOND-Winter simulations (Cycle 1 simulations) (O1)	yes
To perform the Cycle 2 and initiate the Cycle 3 simulations of the Development Phase (O1)	yes
To address errors and fine-tune the SR-ESMs, including associated output and data management strategies, based on feedback from, and together with, the S&R, S&O, S&L themes (O1)	yes
To implement selected applications in SR-ESMs in collaboration with the four themes and users (O3)	yes

Objectives of WP2

Relevance in this deliverable?

To organise scrums to address data management and data analysis workflows in support of Hackathons and simulations analysis within NextGEMS and beyond (O1)

yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Background

The purpose of this report is to summarise the readiness of the SR-ESMs for performing the Cycle 3 nextGEMS simulations, in advance of final preparation for the production simulations. We summarise both the changes made so far for improving ICON and IFS-FESOM/NEMO, and the remaining challenges that are currently being tackled. We also highlight the experiences in organizing and implementing community input through Hackathons, and how this contributed to develop the SR-ESMs and to ensure their usability for the applications.

When discussing readiness of the models in this report, we will distinguish between technical readiness and the readiness of the models in terms of their climate (e.g., tuning).

From ICON, the following nextGEMS Cycle 2 simulations are available:

- two simulations at 10 km resolution covering 30 years, with different thicknesses for the upper ocean layers;
- one 2-year simulation with a horizontal resolution of 5 km; and
- one 3 months long simulation with 2.5 km resolution.

For ICON the plan for Cycle 3 is to run 5–10 years at 5 km and 1–2 years at 2.5 km resolution. In nextGEMS, for all configurations the same horizontal resolution is used in atmosphere and ocean, and for all simulated years the atmospheric forcing of 2020 is applied.

Currently, for the IFS-based models the following simulations are available:

- 2 years at 9 km for the IFS with deep convection on and coupled to 0.25° NEMO version;
- 1 year at 4.4 km for the IFS coupled to FESOM on the NG5 mesh (i.e., resolution of about 13 km in the tropics increasing to 3–5 km in high-latitudes, Fig. 2), and
- 8 months at 2.8 km for the IFS coupled to FESOM employing the NG5 mesh.

For nextGEMS Cycle 3, it is envisaged to run a baseline simulation at 9 km resolution for at least 4 years, and a high-resolution IFS-FESOM simulation for 2–4 years using a 2.8 km/4.4km version of the IFS coupled to the same approximate 4 km multi-resolution version of FESOM (i.e., the NG5 mesh that goes down to 3–5 km resolution).

4.2 ICON

4.2.1 Model climate-readiness

As demonstrated in the previous nextGEMS cycles, ICON can run for several years in the envisioned configurations for Cycle 3. For the ICON system all necessary forcing fields to perform HighResMIP simulations are in principle available and implemented. Those have not been used in the nextGEMS configuration in the last Cycle 2, which rely on perpetual-year 2020 forcing. The climate forcing from greenhouse gas concentration changes, aerosol changes and (background) volcanic forcing still needed to be tested for the planned scenario simulations in nextGEMS, and

the lower boundary conditions over land needed to be provided at high resolution and included in the model.

The largest drawback in long climate integrations with ICON was the large net energy flux imbalance at the top of the atmosphere (-5 W/m^2). This imbalance was caused by an energy leak in the atmosphere component of the model, which lead to model drift and associated biases (e.g., 2 m surface air temperature over land). The leaks were identified in the microphysics, turbulence and dynamics schemes of the model and work focused on solving these issues for the Cycle 3 simulations of nextGEMS. Given the impact of these imbalances on climate, it was decided to refrain from further model tuning of ICON until the energy leaks have been fixed. To this end, the micro-physics and turbulence schemes were rewritten and a diagnostic term was added to the equations of the dynamics. Other updates include new land maps based on high resolution observations, a new vertical coordinate in the ocean to allow for thin layers at the model top and various smaller bug fixes. Additionally, the hydrological discharge from the land to the ocean was adapted to work for thin ocean layers at high resolution. The re-written micro-physics and turbulence are currently tested in preparation for cycle-3. The new vertical coordinate with the thin ocean top layers was already included in the cycle-2 simulations.

4.2.2 Technical readiness

Overall, the technical readiness of the ICON version used in nextGEMS can be considered good. Substantial progress has been made with the atmospheric component of ICON in making effective use of GPUs using OpenACC directives on several compute systems (JSC, CSCS and DKRZ). Depending on the system, this gives an increase in simulation throughput of about a factor of three. The ocean component is still relying on CPUs, but the model can be used in a hybrid configuration, where the atmosphere runs on a GPU cluster and the ocean on the CPU cluster (different parts of the machine) of the same compute center.

ICON has run successfully in atmosphere-only mode at resolutions up to 1 km since the winter 2021/22 on LUMI-C, and an earlier version ran in an idealized and simplified configuration as part of the LUMI-G benchmarks with 2.5 km resolution. A full configuration, with the most recent version of ICON has so far not run on LUMI-G, largely due to limited access to the machine. The porting of ICON to LUMI-G has been ongoing since the autumn of 2021. The work was kicked off with an OpenMP hackathon (Eurohack21) with participants from Hamburg (MPI and DKRZ), Zürich (CSCS), Uppsala (ENCCS) and Stockholm (MISU). Since it became clear that Cray would support the OpenACC directives in the ICON code that runs on JUWELS-Booster at JSC, the development team has been working closely with technologists at CSC, and HPE/Cray to adapt the existing OpenACC implementation to the computational environment of LUMI.

These efforts have already addressed a large number of issues, including compiler bugs, non-standard implementation of OpenACC and the need to port selected CUDA modules to HIP. Given the close collaboration between ICON developers, the computing centers, and vendors, we are confident in our ability to resolve the outstanding issues and soon have a working model that can fully utilize all of the resources that LUMI-G can provide.

Finally, there is ongoing work to optimize the data and workflow. In prototype configurations, ICON can write output on the HEALPix grid (Hierarchical Equal Area isoLatitude Pixelisation), which is prominently used in physical cosmology for mapping the cosmic microwave background. The grid has a series of properties that make it attractive also for storing climate model information, such as pixels of equal size at any given level of the hierarchy (no grid stretching towards

the poles, for example). Furthermore, there is some experimentation with compression and first tests to write to the FDB are being conducted.

4.3 IFS-FESOM/NEMO

4.3.1 Model climate-readiness

Thanks to feedback from the hackathons and work within nextGEMS as well as parallel developments at ECMWF, the IFS-NEMO/FESOM model that is used for the nextGEMS simulations has significantly evolved. The nextGEMS model development efforts have been strategically aligned with model development efforts for ECMWF's operational model. The nextGEMS Cycle 1 simulations were run with IFS Cycle 47r3, which had just been developed before the start of nextGEMS and is operational at ECMWF since October 2021. The first simulations were 75 days long, and were performed with IFS at 9 km with the deep convection scheme on, and at 4.4 km with the deep convection scheme off, both coupled to NEMO at a $0.25 \times 0.25^\circ$ resolution. An additional 4.4 km 40-day long simulation run with IFS (46r1) coupled to FESOM2 ($0.25 \times 0.25^\circ$ resolution) was also performed.

At the first nextGEMS hackathon, strong water and energy imbalances were identified in the nextGEMS Cycle 1 simulations. More specifically, an artificial source of water was identified, responsible for 4.6% of total precipitation in the simulation with deep convection parametrization at 9 km, and for 10.7% without deep convection parametrization at 4.5 km, as well as for an atmospheric energy imbalance of 2.0 W m^{-2} at 9 km, and of 6.4 W m^{-2} at 4.4 km resolution (Figure 1).

Thanks to these hackathon results, a model setup was developed by nextGEMS and ECMWF model development teams in which water vapour, cloud liquid, cloud ice, rain and snow are conserved globally. With these global mass fixers, global water non-conservation was essentially eliminated (about 0.1%) in the nextGEMS Cycle 2 simulations, while the global atmospheric energy budget imbalance reduced to less than 1 W m^{-2} (Figure 1). The improved water and energy conservation turned out to be beneficial not only for long integrations, but also for the quality of ECMWF's medium-range weather forecasts. The model changes performed to fix the water and energy imbalances reduce the overestimate of mean precipitation at different timescales and improved the forecasts skill scores for the upcoming resolution upgrade of medium-range ensembles, and are therefore part of IFS Cycle 48r1 which will become operational in summer 2023 (see article "Fixing water and energy budget imbalances in the Integrated Forecasting System" in ECMWF newsletter 172, <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/elibrary/81312-newsletter-no-172-summer-2022>).

Cycle 2 simulations were therefore performed with an improved model version, in which the water budget changes, and other atmospheric physics and land surface changes developed in parallel at ECMWF for Cycle 48r1, were added to Cycle 47r3. Among these changes are a new multi-layer snow scheme (Arduini et al., 2019), an improved land sea mask and lake representation, a new glacier cover, a revised orographic drag package containing changes to the orographic blocking and turbulent form drag scheme and to the subgrid orography fields (Kanehama et al., 2022).

Regarding ocean improvements, FESOM2 was coupled to the current operational IFS Cycle 47r3. In addition, a new high-resolution ocean grid NG5 was explicitly created for nextGEMS, with resolution ranging between 13 km in the tropics to 4-5 km in mid latitudes and near coasts.

Figure 1: Daily mean water non-conservation (left) and daily mean atmospheric energy imbalance (right), as a function of lead time for IFS nextGEMS Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 simulations. Water non-conservation is computed as the daily change in globally integrated total water, taking account of surface evaporation and precipitation, as a fraction of the daily precipitation.

The simulations in Cycle 2 comprised a 2-year long baseline simulation with IFS at 9 km and NEMO at 0.25° with parameterized deep convection, and an analogous 1-year long simulation without parameterized deep convection. IFS-FESOM2 was run for 12 months and 8 months at 4.4 and 2.8 km resolution in the atmosphere, respectively. Both runs used the NG5 grid in the ocean and had no parameterized deep convection.

In addition to the atmospheric energy imbalance, it is essential for multi-year coupled simulations that the global top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiation imbalance is small. Relative to CERES observations, Cycle 2 showed less of an overestimation of outgoing longwave radiation relative to Cycle 1, reducing the TOA longwave bias. However, the TOA shortwave bias got worse. There was not enough shortwave radiation reflected to begin with, and this bias increased because of the fixes introduced to improve water conservation. In total, the TOA net imbalance deteriorated and was, relative to CERES, about $+2 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ in Cycle 2, while CERES itself shows a $+1 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ imbalance due to anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions. Due to this TOA imbalance, the nextGEMS Cycle 2 simulations warmed too much, by 1–2 K over the course of one year. Thus, addressing the TOA radiation imbalance was a major development focus in preparation for the longer time integrations planned for nextGEMS Cycle 3.

In nextGEMS Cycle 3, we will use the newest model version, IFS Cycle 48r1, which is planned to be implemented operationally at ECMWF in June 2023. Most of the improvements to the model physics implemented in this version were already included in the nextGEMS Cycle 2 configuration. New additions with respect to nextGEMS Cycle 2 are: a radiatively interactive prognostic ozone using new HLO scheme; a new precipitation category: freezing drizzle; a revised computation of Semi-Lagrangian advection departure points; and a new model top sponge layer formulation and semi-Lagrangian vertical filter. A general overview of 48r1 modifications with respect to the previous IFS Cycle 47r3 can be found here:

<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/FCST/Implementation+of+IFS+Cycle+48r1>

On top of IFS Cycle 48r1, in Cycle 3 we will use a combination of model changes targeting to reduce the TOA radiation imbalance, mostly affecting cloud amount. These include: (i) a change restricting the detrainment of mid-level convection to the liquid phase in most situations, (ii) a decrease of a threshold that limits the minimum size of ice effective radius, in agreement with observational evidence, (iii) an adaptation of cloud edge erosion, reducing the general rate

Figure 2: Global-mean monthly 2m temperature (GSAT) in Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 prototype simulations, in comparison to the ERA 5 2017-2021 monthly mean.

of cloud edge erosion but increasing cloud edge erosion when cloud fraction is very small or almost 1. The latter is done by assuming a fixed effective cloud spacing rather than a fixed effective cloud scale, which is in closer agreement with observations (Fielding et al., 2020); (iv) a reduction of the cloud inhomogeneity, which increases cloud amount as it reduces the rate of accretion. This change is in line with nextGEMS's km-scale resolutions as cloud inhomogeneity is expected to be smaller at high resolutions; (v) in agreement with nextGEMS Cycle 2 but unlike in the operational IFS, linear rather than cubic interpolation is used for the departure point interpolation of the Semi-Lagrangian advection scheme for all moist species except water vapour; (vi) a modification of the microphysics for rain and snow evaporation. Instead of using an artificial threshold on relative humidity that prohibits evaporation when relative humidity is above 80%, a sub-grid relative humidity enhancement scheme has been introduced, following the top-hat assumption of Tiedtke (1993), precipitation fraction is reduced proportionally when rain evaporates, and the general rate of rain evaporation has been reduced. Even though not all these model changes will already be implemented in the upcoming IFS Cycle 49r1, they all are considered for future operational IFS Cycles.

A first 1-year prototype simulation for nextGEMS Cycle 3 at 9 km resolution with these model changes targeting the TOA radiation imbalance showed that the net TOA radiation imbalance is indeed reduced to -0.3 W m^{-2} , with a shortwave bias of 0.7 W m^{-2} and a longwave bias of -1 W m^{-2} relative to the CERES EBAF 2001-2021 multi-year average. As a result, the global mean 2m temperature is in the Cycle 3 prototype simulation in close agreement with ERA 5, averaged over 2017-2021, unlike the Cycle 2 simulations which all show a substantial warming (Figure 2).

Another issue is that when the parameterization of deep convection is switched off as it was the case for the 4.4 km and 2.8 km simulations in Cycles 1 and 2, systematic biases are present. Mean precipitation in the tropics is overestimated, particularly over the Pacific ITCZ at 5°N in winter, and individual convective precipitation events tend to be too intense, too short-lived, and too localized. However, when keeping the parameterization of deep convection active, convective precipitation events are too weak and too large, and there is too much precipitation induced

by inertia-gravity wave interaction. Thus, the precipitation characteristics can only be improved by making all moist physics parameterizations (convection, turbulence, clouds, microphysics) ready for storm-resolving scales. In Cycle 3, we are planning to run the simulations at 4.4 km and 2.8 km resolution with an active deep convection scheme but a strongly reduced cloud base mass flux. The weakly active deep convection scheme avoids the formation of too strong convective cells by reducing the convective instability and initialising resolved deep convection more easily. Results for this setup show a good agreement of precipitation intensity with observations and a realistic distribution of zonal mean precipitation. However, mesoscale convective systems like squall lines often fail to be represented, as convective cells are significantly smaller than in observations.

Finally, in Cycle 3 we will also incorporate improvements in the land-surface representation that are most likely part of the next IFS cycle upgrade in 49r1. Among those, there is the representation of cities for the first time within IFS through an urban scheme (McNorton et al., 2021); and improved parameters for snow and frozen soil (Cao et al., 2022; Zsoter et al., 2022); a modified postprocessing of 2m temperature under very stable conditions, and a revised representation of land cover and land use types following ESA-cci products combined with the required vegetation parameter modifications. The revision of land cover and land use types and required vegetation parameter recalibration have been carried out in collaboration with WP8.

We believe that the improved water budget closure and the reduced TOA radiation imbalance are relevant milestones with respect to the IFS climate readiness. However, there are still some aspects of the atmosphere and ocean that need further work. The ocean is too warm in general, leading to an overall warming of the atmosphere too. This shows the critical relevance of an optimal ocean initialization, something that is currently under investigation. An additional warm bias in the southern hemisphere is currently being investigated, too. Initial prototype Cycle 3 runs have shown a reduction of the warm bias when accounting for the ocean cooling caused by melting snow that falls into the ocean, and the remaining warm bias is potentially linked to remaining biases in the Antarctic sea ice extent. For the atmosphere, we will work on further improving the representation of mesoscale organization of deep convection.

4.3.2 Technical readiness

From the beginning of the project, there has been progress in multiple technical aspects to enable climate runs with IFS. In Cycle 1, we used the available workflows at ECMWF for the usual experimentation (i.e., prepIFS, ecfLOW, MARS archiving). In Cycle 2, we already made use of the "Real Applications on Parallel Systems" portable environment (short RAPS) used for benchmarking on other HPCs, which allows for more flexibility in model configuration and versatility as to the HPS being used. In particular, this environment allows to continue runs with restarts in a relatively easy manner, and to modify model settings as needed. Cycle 2 also allowed to write the IFS output directly to files, which was an improvement compared to Cycle 1. In Cycle 1, the simulation output was first archived in MARS at ECMWF and then it was retrieved as grib files, which were finally transferred to DKRZ where the data analysis is performed during the hackathons. In Cycle 2 we provided additional postprocessed data, e.g., monthly means at a coarser $0.25 \times 0.25^\circ$ regular grid, to facilitate a quick analysis of key features of the model climate by project partners during the hackathons, before analysing the high-resolution raw data. Cycle 2 also proved that high-frequency output at selected locations could be produced by IFS for multi-year simulations.

After Cycle 2 there has been significant progress in the technical readiness of IFS-FESOM/NEMO

and the models are now ready for the production of Cycle 3 simulations on multi-annual timescales.

For the nextGEMS Cycle 2 simulations on ECMWF's Atos machine, a significant amount of the overall time was spent in the I/O routines. In those simulations, no I/O server was employed by the IFS yet, and also FESOM2 had been writing serial output (no asynchronous output). Overall, throughput will be increased in Cycle 3 thanks to: (i) reduction in raw model output (e.g., less atmospheric variables, less ocean variables; ocean output just for the upper hundreds of meters), and (ii) use of the more sophisticated available forecast data base software (FDB) and asynchronous I/O option in the IFS with some ocean variables also being processed in this way.

Concerning the output needed for the Hackathon of Cycle 3, we are exploring various directions for how to best provide raw and particularly postprocessed data (e.g., monthly means, remappings to coarser grids). A potential solution, although still not mature, is the use of multi-I/O to perform simple computations (regridding to coarser resolutions and time averages) while in-memory, to avoid the need to load into memory after running IFS for producing the desired fields. The compatibility of the multi-I/O postprocessing pipelines with FDB in its current state is also to be tested. A fall-back procedure for Cycle 3 would be that used for Cycle 2, where monthly means and remappings to coarser grid were performed on the raw grib data with cdo tools after running the simulations. In this regard, any progress done on the use of multi-I/O, even if not used eventually in Cycle 3, is beneficial as this is the planned workflow for the production runs.

Work was also done towards extending IFS capabilities for performing multi-year simulations. This required changes in the source code of IFS to allow for long runs while keeping the possibility for a high frequency (hourly) output. There is currently more work to do on this direction before the production runs can be performed, including the migration of all IFS output to grib2, to better handle future shortcomings in this regard.

Most of the nextGEMS simulations have so far been run on JUWELS (HPC system at Jülich Supercomputing Center, in the framework of a PRACE proposal) and on the new Atos HPC system of ECMWF in Bologna. However, IFS-NEMO/FESOM was also successfully run on LUMI, and Levante (DKRZ), on which some of the Cycle 3 simulations will be performed. While it has been mostly run on CPUs, IFS-FESOM runs in JUWELS have demonstrated the feasibility of a CPU-GPU hybrid approach, in which the spectral transforms (one of the most computationally expensive parts of the IFS) were run on GPUs. There, a 40-day run has been carried out at 2.5 km for IFS-FESOM (with a throughput of 1 SMPD on about 1500 NVIDIA GPUs). NextGEMS Cycle 3 simulations are expected to be performed on Levante (DKRZ) with previous testing carried out on ECMWF's supercomputer, Atos. In parallel, there is ongoing work for trialling IFS-FESOM on LUMI (on the mixed CPU-GPU architecture), to allow realization of some Cycle 3 simulations or the final production runs there provided computing time will become available. A proposal for compute time was submitted to EuroHPC (Klocke and Wedi) and positively evaluated, but the final confirmation is still pending.

4.4 Lessons learned from the previous Hackathons

The first two hackathons were instrumental in revealing model deficiencies which triggered targeted model developments in Cycle 1 and 2 (e.g. the water and energy imbalances in both ICON and IFS, output variables and data organization) The experience of the nextGEMS Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 hackathons has also allowed to revisit the user access to the data. With the high model resolutions that are employed, there are major challenges in handling the large volumes

of output data. We have thus been searching for novel ways to facilitate the user access to the data, as detailed in the following. Moreover, we performed several iterations with our partners regarding the most important model variables to be saved in Cycle 3, which ensures the usability of the provided data by the SR-ESMs for the applications in nextGEMS's four themes (Storm & Land, Storms & Ocean, Storms & Radiation, Storms & Society). A comprehensive analysis of the changes in workflow from the last Cycles can be found in the report for Deliverable 2.3, with a summary of the items to be considered for the Cycle 3 listed below:

Experiment Documentation Contents and format should have a similar standard across all experiments.

Compression, Chunks For ICON, we currently are experimenting with the trade-off between chunk structure and compression, to allow fast regional data access as well as non-degrading global access. To further reduce storage, the use of rounding output data to scientifically significant bits, specific to the different quantities, is currently explored. Furthermore, we are studying more advanced compression algorithms provided via the HDF5 backend of netCDF4, that promise faster decompression at similar compression rates.

Data Storage, Intake Data storage requirements will force us to use a hierarchical model of faster and slower access storage. This includes tape archiving of low-access frequency data together with disk or object storage access for data in frequent use. The intake catalog allows us to implement this hierarchical model while hiding its complexity from the users performing the analysis.

Data Access Towards a common structure for analysis, we will explore use of common grid for both models, as well as the possibility to provide data in different horizontal resolutions instead of just a fixed low-resolution overview version.

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

After delivering to the Commission service, this deliverable will be spread to the members of the consortium via upload of the document to our website <https://nextgems-h2020.eu>.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

The delay was approved by our EC PO.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19.10. – 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 1.4. - 3.4.2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26.06. - 02.07. in Vienna
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>